

ART STUDIES

ORIENTALISM IN CHAMBER VOCAL MUSIC OF R. STRAUSS ON THE EXAMPLE OF THE CYCLE "SONGS OF THE EAST"

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Abstract

From the 17th century to the present day, the theme of the East has been among the interests of composers of different times and nations. As usual, orientalist composers who showed interest in oriental themes interpreted them through the prism of their own musical style, and the nationality of the composer himself also imposed unique features. It is well known that the vocal heritage of R. Strauss is diverse and has been undeservedly underestimated by researchers until now. The subject of analysis of this article is the vocal cycle of R. Strauss. Strauss's vocal cycle "Songs of the East" is a fine example of the late work of the German composer. In it, the composer for the first time turns directly to the original samples of oriental poetry and skilfully combines the musical principles of German song with oriental images. The aim of the article is to provide an insight into and a comparative assessment of orientalism in the composer's chamber vocal music on the example of the song "Ihre Augen" from the cycle "Songs of the East".

Keywords: song, vocal cycle, Orient, Orientalism, Songs of the East, Richard Strauss.

The East has always attracted the attention of Western artists. Enchanting, magical, mystical, this is how it appeared to European man. The fascination of the Western world with the exoticism of the East gave rise to such a cultural phenomenon as Orientalism. Orientalism (from Latin *orientalis* - Eastern) is a recreation of the conventional image of the East, its life and traditions in the work of Western artists. As the famous American literary scholar E. Said writes: "The East (Orient) is almost entirely a European invention, since antiquity it has been a receptacle of romance, exotic creatures, painful and enchanting memories and landscapes, amazing experiences" [1, p. 7].

The theme of the East has always excited the minds of composers of different times: F. Couperin, J. Rameau, W. Mozart, L. van Beethoven, F. Schubert, G. Verdi, J. Brahms, G. Bizet, G. Puccini, H. Wolf, G. Mahler, C. Debussy, E. Satie, M. Ravel, in Russian music - M. Glinka, M. Balakirev, A. Borodin, N. Rimsky-Korsakov, S. Rachmaninov and many other creators. As a rule, composers who showed interest in the theme of the East interpreted it through the prism of their own musical style; the composer's nationality is also superimposed. For example, M. Balakirev's famous "Islamey", despite its clearly traceable oriental flavour, is truly Russian music. It is not by chance that musicologist T. Tikhonova writes: "The model of the Orient in each particular work is connected primarily with the author's individuality, with what is important to him in Eastern culture, as well as with his compositional style" [2].

Thus, in Russian music, the Orient organically entered the work of almost every composer, starting with Glinka and the composers of the "Mighty Handful" and ending with Soviet music. The appeal of Russian composers to Eastern culture forms a special stylistic phenomenon, which has been consolidated in history as 'musical orientalism', "Russian music about the East" (B. Asafiev's terms). This is primarily due to Russia's territorial location, its close ties with China, Japan and other countries of Southeast and Central Asia [3, p.150].

The theme of the East did not immediately become so widespread in the West. The detachment of the Western world, the policy of Eurocentrism in the minds of Europeans, as researchers note, for a long time limited the knowledge of music, literature, painting and culture of Eastern peoples. Only in the second half of the XIX - early XX centuries, European composers began to take an active interest in Eastern music. It is at this time actively establish ties between Europe and Asia. At the beginning of the new century, translations of Oriental poetry into European languages are created, touring performances of ethnographic ensembles, painting exhibitions are held. A landmark event for European art was the performance of ethnic musicians from China, dance ensembles from Java and Indonesian gamelan in 1889 at the World Exhibition in Paris. This served as a significant impetus in the development of interest in the music of Southeast Asia. Thus, C. Debussy, inspired by the sound of the Indonesian gamelan orchestra, wrote the work "Pagodas", which was included in the piano cycle "Estampas". As the writer

V. Hugo accurately noted "...the Orient as a thought or as an image now occupies the imagination and minds of all people... In the age of Louis XIV we were Hellenists, now we are Orientalists. Never have so many minds at the same time fumbled in this great abyss - Asia" [4, p. 135].

German and Austrian composers were also influenced by Eastern music and culture. Composers such as G. Mahler, R. Strauss, A. Schoenberg and A. Webern began to actively address the theme of the East. During his long life, Richard Strauss tried his hand at all musical genres and styles. In the composer's creative diversity there was also a place for the theme of the East, which is the least studied in musicology. As is well known, he first attempted to convey oriental images of ancient Judea in the opera "Salome" (1905). We know from Strauss's diary entries that the composer had long been interested in the world of the East. As the composer noted, "operas on oriental and biblical subjects lack oriental colouring" [5, p. 186]. In the opera "Salome", Strauss finds his own style in "exotic harmony" (Strauss's term). We can also find some oriental elements in the ballet "The Legend of Joseph" (1914) and the opera "Helen of Egypt" (1928), in particular, in the scene where the sons of the desert appear. It is noteworthy that in 1914 R. Strauss travelled through Greece and Egypt. This journey probably enriched him, giving him the inspiration to compose works on oriental ("Songs of the East", Songs Op. 67 from the "West-Eastern Divan") and ancient subjects (the operas "Ariadne on Naxos", "Daphne" and "The Love of Danae"). Already on the slope of his years, in 1940 the composer wrote a symphonic work entitled "Japanese Solemn Music". Here the composer shows himself as a powerful symphonist, an heir to the traditions of Wagner and Brahms. However, this work, the music of which corresponds entirely to the genre of the symphonic poem, lacks the rich oriental flavour. Interestingly, "Japanese Solemn Music" was written at the height of the Second World War (1940) and dedicated to the Emperor of Japan.

Strauss's vocal legacy is the least studied layer of the great composer's work. Over the course of his long life, the composer expressed his most intimate thoughts and feelings in them. At the same time, it was a kind of laboratory in which Strauss perfected his unique compositional style. During his long, creative life, the composer, according to various estimates, wrote more than 200 songs, but unfortunately only a few of them are performed today. For a long time the composer's vocal work was undeservedly overshadowed by opera and symphony. Only in the last two decades has there been an active study of the composer's unique song heritage.

In his vocal works Strauss is entirely in line with the German and Austrian song tradition. As the musicologist E. Krause writes, "there is no doubt that Strauss the lyricist originated from Schubert, Schumann and, mainly, Liszt" [6, p. 290].

"Songs of the East" was written by the composer in 1928 and belongs to the late period of his work. The appeal to the theme of the East was dictated by the general interest of the Western world in the enchanting images of Eastern aesthetics. It is important to note that the East is shown in the most personal genre for the composer - the song. As is well known, many researchers divide Strauss's song works into several groups: love lyrics, landscape lyrics, satirical, social, lyric-psychological, philosophical. Researcher O. Alferova in her work "The Vocal Cycle of R. Strauss Flower Girls: to the problem of style" singles out the vocal cycles "Songs of the East" and "Lotus Petals" in a separate group (Songs inspired by images of the East) [7]. It should be noted that in the cycle "Songs of the East" Strauss for the first time directly addresses oriental poetry. The vocal cycle Songs of the East for soprano is based on the words of Persian poet Shirazi Hafiz and Chinese classical poetry translated by Hans Bethge. Songs No. 1, 2, 4 and 5 were written based on Hafiz, and the song "Liebesgeschenke" ("Gifts of Love") from the Chinese Flute. The special interest of the German Romantics in the poetic heritage of the Persian poet Hafiz should be emphasised. This was particularly evident in the works of Brahms and Wolf. Shirazi Hafiz (circa 1225-1300) was a Persian poet and Sufi sheikh whose poems are the pinnacle of Persian poetry, especially in the ghazal genre. Let us recall that the genre of ghazal (small lyric poem), as researchers point out, reaches its perfect embodiment in the works of Hafiz. They extensively praise sensual, earthly love. Hafiz's poetry, as M. Kurgantsev, one of the researchers of the poet's heritage, emphasises, is a new frontier of world lyrics, an important step on the way to comprehending the human heart [8, p. 10]. The peculiarity of Hafiz's lyrics lies in the fact that it is earthly love that appears in the ghazals as the greatest value of existence, as a force equal in its irresistibility to the natural elements. The triumph of love according to Hafiz is a verdict to the forces of evil, lies and violence, as modern French poet Louis Aragon said "Speak only of love, everything else is a crime" [8, p. 12]. The vocal cycle is dedicated to the singer Elisabeth Schumann and her husband, the conductor Carl Alwin, with whom Strauss had a long association. Many of the vocal works were written especially for E. Schumann and performed by this remarkable vocalist of the twentieth century.

Hans Bethge
(1876-1946)

Richard Strauss's appeal to Chinese poetry is noteworthy. It should be said that the collection of translations *The Chinese Flute* was a landmark for twentieth-century music. Published by H. Bethge in 1907, it was the first major publication to include free translations of classical Chinese poetry. Poems from *The Chinese Flute* became the literary basis for works by G. Mahler, R. Strauss, K. Szymanowski, B. Martinů, A. Schoenberg, A. Webern, K. Penderecki and many other contemporary composers. The cycle *Songs of the East* clearly shows a connection with Mahler and his "Song of the Earth" (1909), as indicated by the literary basis and form of the Strauss cycle. "Song of the Earth" is a symphony in songs by Gustav Mahler for two soloists and orchestra. In form, the symphony is close to a vocal cycle, which brings it closer to Strauss's *Songs*. At different times the work "Songs of the East" has had polar assessments and significance in the composer's work. For example, E. Krause, a researcher of Strauss's works, assesses this cycle as "devoid of cogency", which, in our opinion, sounds subjective [6, p. 298]. Strauss's work is currently being reinterpreted, undeservedly forgotten works are being restored and their significance is being reassessed. Today, the cycle is still rarely found in the repertoire of performers. In the mid-twentieth century, the songs were part of the repertoire of the famous German baritone Dietrich Fischer-Dieskau. In co-operation with the brilliant accompanist Gerald Moore, he performed many of Strauss's vocal works. In his autobiographical book "Singer and Accompanist" G. Moore examines in detail some of Strauss's songs, giving them a high artistic assessment [9, pp. 245-251]. The main theme of the cycle "Songs of the East" is connected with love lyrics, with asceticism, philosophy, metaphorical expression characteristic of oriental poetry. R. Strauss takes his own approach to the embodiment of the images of the East. There is almost no artificial imitation in the cycle. The composer interprets the East in an original way, trying to avoid classical stamps, refraining from the ornamentation characteristic of the East in the melodic line and the complexity of the rhythmic pattern, while at the same time complicating the harmonic language and polyphonic fabric. Here we

see a mature master whose works are characterised by complex harmonic structures and clarity of form.

The vocal cycle "Songs of the East" has a lyrical and romantic character, which is generally typical of the composer's vocal work. One of the features of the cycle is the interpretation of the piano part, in which, in our opinion, the central core, the "East" itself, is concentrated. The piano texture creates allusions to impressionism, referring us to works by Satie, Debussy and Ravel. The sequence of songs is given according to the principle of contrast – key-scale, size, tempo, texture, shape, character. Strauss builds a cycle from the most clear and transparent in texture and melodic line of the song "Ihre Augen" ("Her eyes") to the last "Huldigung" ("Worship") with her complex vocal part with an abundance of chromaticisms, deviations and texturally complex piano accompaniment.

«Ihre Augen»

The cycle opens with the song "Ihre Augen" ("Her eyes") by Hafiz, which celebrates the enchanting beauty of women. Below we present the literary text of the song – the German original and the English translation of the authors of the work:

<i>Deine gewölbten Brauen, O Geliebte, sind Paradieseslauben, darunter lächelnd die holden Engel deiner Augen wohnen.</i>	<i>Your arched brows, O beloved, Are bowers of para- dise; smiling below Them, those sweet an- gels, your eyes, abide.</i>
<i>Der Glanz, der durch die Welt gebreitet ist, geht aus von diesen Engeln, die den Schimmer mitbrachten aus der Flur des Paradieses!</i>	<i>A gleam, spread throughout the world, Goes forth from these angels who brought with them The lustre from the fields of Paradise!</i>

Obviously, one of the most interesting questions is the author's approach to the creation of Eastern images and the ways of their embodiment. When analysing the interaction between the Western and the Eastern, we take into account the theory of multidimensionality put

forward by Y. Azarova, in which the interaction of different cultures (West and East) is traced at three levels of composition: semantic, stylistic and architectonic. The semantic level implies familiarity with religious and philosophical ideas of Buddhism, Taoism, Confucianism. The principles of “connection of opposites” (yin-yang), “non-action” (wu-wei), “completeness” (dharma), “emptiness” (shunyata). The stylistic level involves borrowing not so much the actual musical material as its spiritual code, which represents the Eastern way of thinking, Eastern colour (intonation, rhythm, metre, timbre, register). The architectonic level involves the creation of new original artistic forms [10, p.165-155].

It is noteworthy that, having numerous examples of the embodiment of images of the East (Schumann,

Mendelssohn, Brahms and Wolf), R. Strauss approaches the embodiment of images of the East in his own way. There is almost no artificial imitation in the cycle. In his endeavour to show the East, the composer tries to avoid in his music the stamps developed in the work of his predecessors, refraining from the ornamentation characteristic of the East in the melodic line and the complexity of the rhythmic pattern, but at the same time complicating the harmonic language and polyphonic fabric. However, from the first bars of the piano introduction, in the shimmering eighth notes in the right hand (major pentatonic), one can clearly hear the oriental spirit of the cycle:

Richard Strauss, Op. 77 № 1

Moderato

Piano

Figure 1. R. Strauss, “Songs of the East”, “Ihre Augen”, introduction theme

According to the composer's comments, he uses in the cycle a through-form characteristic of the vocal works of F. Liszt and H. Wolf. An extended piano introduction (an extended period of 10 bars) precedes the vocal part. The tempo is Moderato, tonality C-dur, the melody is cantilinal in character. The song is characterized by a small tessitura from a1 - h2 (A of the first octave - B of the second). The flexible plasticity of the vocal melody, the subtlety of the harmonies and the refinement of the piano texture correspond to the image that dominates Hafiz's poetic text.

One of the characteristic features of the composer's construction of the tonal plan is the frequent absence of signs in the key, caused by frequent deviations in tonality of both close and distant affinities (in the future, the parallel major-minor serves as a basis for such “colouring” through the introduction of side septactic chords and their resolution).

We note the surprising interrelation of poetic and vocal beginnings, which conveys the semantic nuances and individual subtleties of the poetic text and even the structure of the Oriental poet's verse. The latter can be defined as one of the typical features inherent in the song style of Strauss, who said: “the verse gives birth

to the vocal melody, and the piano amplifies and deepens the content” [6, p. 294].

It is significant that the composer's creative experiments in this sphere testify to the support and development of the trend formed in the vocal music of H. Wolf, G. Mahler and M. Reger. It should be recalled that the names of these composers are associated with the emergence of such a new genre hybrid, a type of song, as “poem with music”. This genre innovation V. Vasina-Grossman calls “the most characteristic in the lyrics of the last third of the XIX - early XX century” [11, p. 304]. According to the composer himself, who gave priority to verse over vocal melody, such an intellectual problem as the relationship between music and words, the correlation between the poetic text and melody, was constantly in the centre of his attention, as were many other brilliant creators.

The song “Ihre Augen” is one of the most vivid and imaginative in the cycle. It organically combines the principles of romantic German song and impressionism, manifested in particular in the harmonic sphere, the use of harmonic shimmers and pentatonic passages in the piano part. Arpeggiato chords and triol pulsation give a specific oriental lightness and clarity to the melodic pattern:

Figure 2. R. Strauss, "Songs of the East", "Ihre Augen", piano texture fragment

The beginning of the vocal part exactly repeats the melodic line set out in the first bars of the accompaniment. The texture in the piano part is extremely varied. Based on the existing nine types of piano accompaniment, one can confidently say that the use and alternation of various types of texture is masterly.

Already in the introduction one finds a characteristic feature of the song - the complete independence of the piano part. But despite the apparent "freedom" of

the accompaniment, the piano entirely follows the vocal part, often duplicating the soloist's theme: the piano finishes the soloist's work, continues the development of the thematic material during pauses or sustained notes. Three solo piano conceptions can be distinguished throughout the song:

Introduction (Prelude) The most significant piano conduction (10 bars). The piano introduction precedes the soloist and contains the intonations of the vocal part:

Figure 3. R. Strauss, "Songs of the East", "Ihre Augen", holding the main vocal theme in the piano part

Middle section (interlude) The middle is a 4-stroke passage. It serves as a preparation for the climax of the piece: it begins with *pp* followed by *cresc.*, in the last bar and an exit on *f*, literally leading to the 'top of the

source" (tension, tessitura). In the soloist's part, the climax is given on the B-flat note of the second octave on the word "Der Glanz" ("Shine"):

Figure 4. R. Strauss, "Songs of the East", "Ihre Augen", middle piano interlude

The tonal plan is G-dur, e-moll, Ges-dur. In this fragment, R. Strauss turns to the sound imitation of instrumental tunes and overdubs, which are pentatonic in their basis.

The conclusion (postlude) is a kind of emotional and semantic quintessence of the main idea of the song, despite its six-stroke form. Let us highlight the harmonic diversity of this fragment, in which functional harmony acquires a phonetic role - colouristic, out of

harmonic context. In this way we can see features of modality (and impressionism in the European context) in the work of R. Strauss. The composer's virtuoso manner of handling the tonal plan is characteristic of

the composer, and the further completion in C-dur follows:

Figure 5. R. Strauss, "Songs of the East", "Thre Augen", piano postlude

We should also note such a feature as the presence of large solo passages in the piano part, in which the development of motifs of musical material is observed. The presentation of solo fragments is also correlated with "musical" layers. This allows us to speak of the composer's inherent method of bringing the vocal cycle closer to the genres of symphonic music. The same principle is maintained by the composer in the following songs of the cycle.

In comprehending the poetry of Hafiz, the master of the ghazal, R. Strauss also adheres, as he said, to the model and style he found in the other songs of the cycle based on poems by the oriental poet - "Schwung", "Die Allmächtige" and "Huldigung". In these songs he managed to find an intonation and melodic sphere imbued with subtle psychology, an interesting metrical organisation and a flexible form. In terms of melodic pattern, harmonic language and texture, the influence of Eastern culture can also be traced. Strauss's intension to create a West-Eastern synthesis, manifested in the subtle combination of the musical features of two different cultures, comprehension of the other essence and the ability to discover it in his music, is a powerful factor in renewing and enriching not only the themes, imagery and musical language, but also the very principles of the approach to musical material in this innovative vocal cycle.

Thus, in the vocal heritage of R. Strauss, a special place is occupied by works related to Eastern culture, themes and images of the East. The vocal cycle "Songs of the East", based on Hafiz, is an artistic phenomenon of the late Romantic style. Richard Strauss, a daring innovator, connected in his search for the renewal of musical language, style and genres with new artistic trends in musical art - Expressionism (a forerunner of Expressionism), Impressionism, Symbolism, Neoclassicism, remains to a greater extent an adherent of the traditions developed in the works of F. Schubert, R. Schumann, J. Brahms, H. Wolf, the last Romantic. Strauss's vocal cycle "Songs of the East" is Strauss's significant musical steps towards the culture of the East, serving as a

confirmation of the fact that one of the characteristic features of modern culture is the tendency to connect the seemingly incommunicable, the interaction between the cultures of the West and the East, leading to the contact between the past and the modern, the traditional and the new, the Western and the Eastern.

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